

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP4 – Establishment of a non-commercial, Europe-wide breast milk biobank and analytical centre

D4.10 Way of working of Scientific Governance Board and members

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Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.1	11 09 2024	Draft sent to Uppsala Biobank
V1.2	11 10 2024	Revised draft sent to the team WP 4
V1.3	04 11 2024	Revised draft sent to the Managing Board

Abstract

In the Framework of ConcePTION five human lactation demonstration studies have been carried out, investigating the effects of medicines (amoxicillin, levocetirizine, metformin, prednisolone and venlafaxine) taken during breastfeeding to help women make informed decisions about taking medicines during breastfeeding. The collected samples are stored at Uppsala Biobank in accordance with Swedish legislative and regulatory frameworks for biobanking of tissue and blood samples. Use of this governance structure in other countries and for other sample collections need to be based on amendments fitting respective legislative frameworks. Any future research may only be allowed if it is in accordance with the ethics approval for the sample collection. The proposed study must be approved by an appropriate ethics review board.

- The samples must be coded.
- The samples must be returned, destroyed or de-identified when they are no longer needed for the purpose for which they were sent.

Besides investigating transfer of medicines to breast feeding infants the purpose of the ConcePTION sample collections is to enable future research related to lactation and medication. In order to make sample collections of breast milk and associated plasma samples visible the European research infrastructure BBMRI-ERIC will initiate a special on-line directory of breast milk for research collections through which researchers in the field may identify samples and associated data that may be of interest to them.

Methods

This governance structure was drafted based on established models at Uppsala Biobank and subsequently revised in accordance with discussions within the ConcePTION WP4 Team.

Results

Governance structure for IMI-ConcePTION Sample Collections of breast milk and associated plasma samples from breast feeding women under medication and their infants

This governance structure is a deliverable from Work Package 4 of the IMI-ConcePTION project. The ConcePTION project has received funding from the Innovative Medicines Initiative 2 Joint Undertaking under grant agreement no. 821520. This Joint Undertaking receives support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and EFPIA.

Introduction

In the Framework of ConcePTION five human lactation demonstration studies have been carried out, investigating the effects of medicines (amoxicillin, levocetirizine, metformin, prednisolone and venlafaxine) taken during breastfeeding to help women make informed decisions about taking medicines during breastfeeding.

The investigator driven demonstration studies performed within ConcePTION have been set up according to standardised protocols. All protocols have been approved by appropriate ethical review boards and regulatory authorities and registered at EU-PAS displayed in the HMA-EMA Catalogues, EudraCT and followed ICH-GCP requirements. The protocols are accessible as described below.

1. The protocol for the levocetirizine study: “Levocetirizine/cetirizine levels in human milk – an observational, clinical study among breastfeeding women”. **EUPAS46213**.
2. The protocol for the venlafaxine study: “Prediction of venlafaxine exposure trough breastfeeding”. **EUPAS103385**.
3. The protocol for the amoxicilline study: “Evaluation of Amoxicillin diffusion in breast milk according to a population pharmacokinetic approach”. **N°EudraCT 2021-002247-30**.
4. The protocol for the metformin study: « Transfer of metformin into human breast milk and the plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention trial with biobanking of breast milk and plasma in Västra Götalandsregionen and Region Örebro”. **EUPAS 105190, CTIS 2022-501693-19-00**.
5. The protocol for the prednisolone study: “Transfer of prednisolone into human breast milk and plasma of breastfeeding children - A low intervention cohort study with biobanking of breast milk and plasma”. **EUPAS 1000000059, CTIS 2023-508913-18-00**.

The collected samples are stored at Uppsala Biobank in accordance with Swedish legislative and regulatory frameworks for biobanking of tissue and blood samples. Use of this governance structure in other countries and for other sample collections need to be based on amendments fitting respective legislative frameworks.

Organisational premises – Uppsala Biobank

Uppsala Biobank has two principals, Region Uppsala, which is represented by the Akademiska University Hospital, and Uppsala University, which is represented by the Faculty of Medicine in the field of Medical and Pharmaceutical science. Uppsala Biobank is the joint and only biobank within the principals and all biobank samples within these two principals must be incorporated as a sample collection in Uppsala Biobank. The head of Uppsala Biobank is responsible for all biobank samples and sample collections within the principals' operations, research sample collections, sample collections intended for care, diagnostics and treatment (VDB) and biobank samples intended for other approved purposes.

From 1 January 2010, Uppsala Biobank and UCR Laboratory together are organised as a section at UCR (Uppsala Clinical Research). UCR is its own center formation that is organisationally linked to the Science Area for Medicine and Pharmacy at Uppsala University and to the University Hospital. UCR Laboratory is part of Uppsala Biobank and offers services for biomarker analysis as well as different type of sample handling. A Biobank Council with representatives from the principals is linked to Uppsala Biobank. The Biobanks Council consists of expert representatives from the principals, a chairman and four members, and has a decision-making, advisory and reviewing function in the event of conflicts and in the conclusion or handling of sample collections.

The Biobanks Council consists of expert representatives from the principals, a chairman and six members. The chairman is the region's biobank coordinator, who is appointed by the regional director. Three members represent the Akademiska University Hospital and are appointed by the hospital director. Three members represent the university and are appointed by the Faculty Board of Medicine and Pharmacy. All members are

appointed for a period of 3 years and the assignment can be held for several consecutive periods. The Biobanks Council meets at least twice per semester and the meetings are recorded in minutes. The head and biobank custodian of Uppsala Biobank is the rapporteur in the Biobank Council.

According to law, the principals, in this case Region Uppsala represented by the Akademiska University Hospital (healthcare principal) and Uppsala University (research principal) must decide in conflicts of interest concerning biobank samples, biobank sample collections or other biobank-related issues. Through this agreement, Uppsala Biobank's principals instruct the Biobank Council to represent them in this role. The Biobank Council thus has a decisive role in conflicts between:

- Uppsala Biobank and a sample collection controller, contact person or principal investigator (PI).
- A sample collection controller and another researcher on taking biobank samples.
- A sample collection controller and another researcher / controller / company regarding the distribution of biobank samples.
- The Biobank Council further decides whether a sample collection should be terminated or saved. This includes assessing the scientific value of sample collections.

Uppsala Biobank has registration number 827 with the supervisory authority, the Swedish Health and Care Inspectorate (IVO). The Biobank custodian has the ultimate responsibility for ensuring that Uppsala Biobank's assignment is fulfilled.

Head and biobank custodian: Anna Beskow
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Contact information for Uppsala Biobank

Postal and visiting address: Uppsala Biobank, Dag Hammarskjölds väg 38, 5 tr, 751 85 Uppsala.

Website: www.uppsalabiobank.uu.se.

Email: info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se. Employees at Uppsala Biobank have email addresses according to name.lastname@uppsalabiobank.uu.se.

Sample collection controller for research sample collections

Each research sample collection in Uppsala Biobank has a sample collection controller and a contact person (can be the same person). For each research sample collection, a legally reviewed and approved agreement, "Assignment description for sample collection controller for research sample collection in Uppsala Biobank". This agreement is signed by both the biobank custodian and the sample collection controller. For the IMI-ConcePTION studies the Principal Investigator is the collection controller and contact person of respective sample collections.

Principal investigators and collection controllers are:

1. For the levocetirizine study: Dr. Hedvig Marie Egeland Nordeng, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway.
2. For the amoxicilline study: Dr. Peggy Gandia, Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Toulouse, Toulouse, France.
3. For the venlafaxine study: Dr. Alica Panchaud, University of Geneva and University Hospital in Lausanne, Lausanne, Switzerland.
4. For the metformin and prednisolone studies: Dr. Mats Hansson, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden.

Through the agreement, the person responsible for the sample collection will have the right to dispose of the samples in a research sample collection, which means an unlimited right to use samples in their own research that has been approved by the Ethics Review Board.

The sample collection controller is responsible for:

- Handling and documenting the biobank samples in accordance with the approved ethics application, applicable laws and regulations as well as local rules and guidelines.
- Ensuring all biobank samples are traceable according to the Swedish Biobank Act and that changes in the sample collection are documented in a traceable manner.
- Ensuring that the safety requirements imposed on the handling and storing of biobank samples in current laws and regulations are met. Reports of major discrepancies in the sample collection stored in Uppsala Biobank are to be sent to info@uppsalabiobank.uu.se.
- Documentation of approved ethics applications with appendices, as well as ongoing and completed studies.
- Reporting the release of samples to another principal to Uppsala Biobank. Release of samples can only take place if the sample collection controller and biobank custodian approve this. Uppsala Biobank then make an agreement with the biobank custodian at the receiving biobank using the national templates.
- Informing Uppsala Biobank when the sample collection controller is changed. Uppsala Biobank then prepares an assignment description with a new sample collection controller.
- Reporting to Uppsala Biobank when you wish to end a sample collection or when there is a desire for Uppsala Biobank to take over responsibility for a sample collection. The decision on whether a sample collection should be terminated or the responsibility will be transferred is made by the Biobank Council.

Use of samples for research

Any future research may only be allowed if it is in accordance with the explicit and signed informed consent by the participant who has provided the samples as an ethics approval for the sample collection. The proposed study must be approved by an appropriate ethics review board.

- The samples must be coded.
- The samples must be returned, destroyed or de-identified when they are no longer needed for the purpose for which they were sent.

When biobank samples are sent for analysis, an "MTA AGREEMENT on the transfer of biological material" must always be established. This agreement regulates the parties' liability when biobank samples with associated coded personal data are transferred from a Swedish controller to a foreign recipient. Instructions and template for MTA are available at the Biobank Sweden website (www.biobanksverige.se). The Swedish Biobanks Act does not allow Swedish biobank samples to be stored or handed over to a foreign personal data controller. According to the Swedish Biobanks Act, the term biobank includes both human biological material and the information linked to the sample donor. When sending samples for analysis abroad, you must therefore do so in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Coded biobank samples may be sent for analysis abroad to countries within the EU and the EEA, and to so-called third countries that are not members of the EU or EEA but have an adequate level of protection according to the Data Inspectorate and laboratories that are approved according to the Safe Harbor principles. Updated information on third country transfers, Safe Harbor principles and adequate level of protection is available at the Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection website (www.datainspektionen.se). The patient or sample donor must always have consented to the sample being sent for analysis abroad.

Instructions and templates of the Material Transfer Agreements to be used are published on the Biobank Sweden website (<http://www.biobanksverige.se>)

Making sample collections for research findable – The BBMRI-Directory

Besides investigating transfer of medicinal substances from mothers to breast feeding infants the purpose of the ConcePTION sample collections is to enable future research related to the safety of lactation during medication. In order to make sample collections of breast milk and associated plasma samples visible the European research infrastructure of biobanks and biomolecular resources BBMRI-ERIC will showcase networks of breast milk for research collections in The BBMRI-ERIC Directory (directory.bbmri-eric.eu) through which researchers in the field may easily identify sample collections that may be of interest to them.

In the first stage the Directory will include only sample collections that were part of or associated to the ConcePTION project. The plan is then to invite new sample collections to be part of the network and thus

making breast milk samples available for research related to medication. The additional breast milk sample collections may come from an academic or an industry context. The access to the sample collections is guided by the following premises:

1. The PI of the sample collections is the sole controller and contact person.
2. Any use of the samples must abide with GDPR and the national law of the country where the samples were collected.
3. Only use that is consistent with the informed consent by the participant who has provided the sample and an ethical permit of the collection is allowed.
4. Any use for future research must abide with GDPR and the national law of the country where the research is to be carried out and ethical approval must be obtained for the planned research.
5. Following the Vancouver regulations for authorship the PI for the sample collections shall always be offered co-authorship for any publication that emanates from the sample collection.

Governing Board

For the IMI-ConcePTION sample collections a multi-disciplinary Governing Board has been established. It consists of the principal investigators of the five demonstration studies and a representative of EFPIA. The EFPIA representative is yet to be nominated. The role of the governing board is to give advice to sample controllers regarding requests for use. Questions to be addressed are:

1. Is the intended use consistent with the informed consent and the ethics approval?
2. Is the intended use scientifically sound?
3. In terms of shortage of samples, is the intended use of high priority from a scientific point of view?

Discussion

No changes

Conclusion

The governance structure is as described above.

Repository for primary data

N/A